

ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION AS A MEANS OF MOTIVATION FOR LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation. The importance of control at different stages of learning a foreign language is emphasized. The need for objective assessment and marking during learning is substantiated, since there is a close relationship between assessment and the formation, maintenance and strengthening of motivation in mastering a foreign language. It is concluded that an objective, comprehensive assessment is an important motivating stimulus for a student and an effective tool in a teacher's arsenal.

Key words: control, assessment, marking, motivation, maintenance and strengthening.

The need to improve various types of control for a reliable and objective assessment of the results achieved by students is one of the most discussed topics in pedagogy, especially when teaching a foreign language.

Currently, due to fierce competition in the labor market, the need for highly qualified specialists who are able to communicate in a foreign language is steadily increasing. However, we live not only to solve economic problems, but educational tasks are no less important.

Nowadays, students have ample opportunities to travel for exchange studies and receive education at educational institutions in different countries. It is natural that such an important question of assessment arises here, how high-quality is the preparation of students in terms of language. The problem of assessment was and is one of the most important components of the educational process at all stages of teaching a foreign language. With the help of control and evaluation, a number of different functions are carried out: teaching, predicting, diagnosing, developing and, of course, educational. Without a doubt, the further desire to continue studying and, as a consequence, the entire learning outcome depends on how well control and assessment is organized. To put it differently, assessment is one of the very

significant means of motivating students when learning a foreign language at all stages of learning.

If we compare the meaning of the concepts: “assessment” and “mark”, then it becomes obvious that they are not identical. The mark is a point indicator that is established by state standards in order to indicate the degree of knowledge of each specific student. An assessment can be called a verbal (verbal) description of the results, diligence, aspirations, efforts on the part of the student; often the assessment is of a detailed nature.

The mark should follow from the assessment, but not vice versa. Giving a mark should be a natural result of the process of monitoring and assessing students’ skills. The mark is most often a quantitative characteristic, which is expressed by the total amount of points, summed up from the assessments of each of the criteria of the controlled skill. Here are several problems that a teacher may encounter:

- how to create a diagram that would clearly reflect the assessment;
- how to remain fair when assessing students;
- how to assess students’ skills in various types of speech activity;
- how to find an individual approach to a student;
- how to expand the vector of assessment from a focus on external control to improving learning achievements (learning outcomes), as well as increasing the interest (motivation) of students in learning a foreign language.

If we follow the meaning of such terms as “control”, “check”, “assessment” in domestic didactics, we will find that they are often used as synonyms and complement each other. With regard to testing learning outcomes or control, these terms are usually considered as pedagogical diagnostics. Assessment in didactics usually refers to the process of comparing the level that students managed to achieve with the standard concepts described in the curriculum.

Regarding the process itself, the assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out during control or verification of the latter. The conventionally accepted reflection of the assessment is a mark, which is usually expressed in points. Expressed in the form of a mark (in points) or a verbal value judgment by the teacher.

...Testing and evaluation include determining the goals and objectives of training, requirements for learning outcomes at each stage of the educational process; selection of test tasks, examples and method of expressing test results. All

components of verification and assessment are interrelated and must be considered as a unity.”

For the normal implementation of any human activity, motivation is necessary. It is of particular importance for cognition, and in the process of teaching a foreign language at each of the individual stages its role is very large. Psychologists traditionally distinguish between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

Intrinsic motivation can be associated with the effectiveness of educational activities, with the satisfaction of the need to improve performance results.

Exploratory behavior involves a person’s subjective assessment of his skills in relation to solving problems or situations facing him.

Psychology has not yet come to a consensus in understanding what motivation essentially is and what its role is in regulating human behavior.

However, even if on the part of students the desire to communicate in a foreign language is pronounced, it is the above type of motivation that is most difficult to maintain and maintain. That is why the assessment must be realistic, it must be based on comparison with the student's earlier achievements and results, since comparing the progress that the student has made relative to himself is much more appropriate than a simple comparison based on standards alone.

It is this assessment that contributes not only to maintaining, but also to increasing learning motivation and positive self-perception.

An important goal of good assessment should be to create and strengthen feedback between the student and the teacher.

This, in turn, would give the teacher the opportunity to motivate the student, develop his desire to learn, and stimulate knowledge. It would also serve as an impetus for further self-improvement of students, allowing them to independently evaluate and objectively analyze the achievements and results of their educational activities.

Assessment and marks should be used as a means that would encourage the student to actively work, in other words, marks should be used as a powerful motivating tool.

Assessment is a powerful educational tool that influences the development of the individual as a whole. Consequently, assessment affects all areas of a child’s life, regulates his relationships with others, and helps make plans for the future. The influence of assessment becomes beneficial if the student has confidence in the

teacher, where the decisive role is played by the teacher’s personality, his expectations, general position, style of communication with the class, and the ability to create an atmosphere of psychological comfort.”

All of the above is also true for students studying a foreign language. If there is no success, this will inevitably lead to the fading of its results, it should help the teacher select the most effective techniques and means of teaching that could stimulate the development of students, their further motivation, and which, in turn, will negatively affect educational activities .

Evaluation on the one hand of the process of cognition itself, and on the other hand, progress in learning a foreign language. If we conclude from here that an equally important task of a foreign language teacher is to expand the zone of external motivation in various ways. On the other hand, the teacher must focus on the student’s internal motivation, his current tasks and needs; develop interest in a foreign language.

The most important question that every teacher needs to find an answer to at the stage of knowledge control, regardless of what subject he teaches, including foreign language teachers, is “How to objectively and impartially evaluate a student without belittling his human dignity, How can we make assessment not only educational and educational, but also, to a large extent, a motivating factor?” When working with students, it is necessary to use all types of control for visual and objective assessment and marking:

1. Introductory, allowing to assess the level of students’ knowledge and general erudition. To do this, you can use testing, conversation, questioning, observation.
2. Current, which allows you to assess the degree of mastery of educational material on a specific topic, educational unit, for which diagnostic tasks are well suited, namely: surveys, tasks and practical work, various types of testing.
3. Corrective, allowing to identify and eliminate gaps and shortcomings. To do this, we can offer the use of repeated tests, as well as individual consultations, allowing for an individual approach to the student.
4. Final, which makes it possible to assess the degree of completion of the assigned tasks. Here, different types of reading, translation, annotation, testing and other types of tasks are used to assess various aspects.

In foreign language classes, students' knowledge can be assessed through frontal and individual work. With a frontal survey, in a short period of time it is possible to assess the state of knowledge of all students in each group.

An individual oral survey allows you to assess the correctness of the answer in terms of content, its consistency, independence of judgment, the logic of constructing a statement, and the speech culture of each student. This form is used for current and thematic accounting.

Oral questioning is carried out at every lesson; correct assessment of students' knowledge plays an important role here. Testing in written form allows you to assess the knowledge of a large number of students simultaneously in a short time. Students' written work is carried out in the form of control, verification and independent work, tests.

Increasingly, we began to use tests to test knowledge. The test allows you to quickly and relatively simply, under equal conditions for all subjects, make an assessment. At the same time, it is very important not to stop only at assigning points for the completed test, but to analyze its results, giving a detailed assessment of the result.

The exam is conducted to determine the achievement of the final learning outcomes on a specific topic by each student. At this stage, you should also not limit yourself to just setting a point mark. This stage is very important in terms of motivation and requires special attention from the teacher. If we talk specifically about the process of teaching foreign languages within a university, we can conclude that a foreign language, being one of the few humanitarian disciplines in the educational cycle, has all the capabilities to solve not only educational, but also a whole range of educational tasks in the formation of personality future professionals.

The assessment, in turn, must be effective and comprehensive. It should be based on objective indicators, allow the process of determining the final grade to be formalized, provide feedback, and the system should also be flexible enough.

All this will stimulate motivation to learn a foreign language, which, in turn, will improve the quality of specialist training.

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